

Hello and welcome to the second LNL newsletter edited by me, David Smailes, as part of my role as Chair of the Local Network Leads.

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LNL News

First, a reminder that the 2025 LNL Summer Retreat will be on Monday 2nd and Tuesday 3rd June 2025 at the London School of Economics and Political Science (LSE), London. There should be an email in your inbox re: this (from 21/FEB/2025). But info is also available at the top of the registration form (please register!): <https://forms.office.com/e/2RnyK6rubE>

LNL Spotlight

This month, I'm nudging you in the direction of this - [youtube.com/watch?v=EFtL0fgy_o](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EFtL0fgy_o) - brief talk by Josefina Weinerova (LNL at Nottingham), in which she presents her pre-registration for a study on the effects of COVID-19 on cognitive and brain function, using data from UK Biobank. Have a watch to find out a little bit more about the work of one of your fellow LNLs.

Job Opportunities

A very interesting looking post with one of our LNLs - Dr Charlotte Pennington - is being advertised here - <https://www.jobs.ac.uk/job/DMH995/research-associate> - on [jobs.ac.uk](https://www.jobs.ac.uk).

Meanwhile, PLOS have several positions out for advert in their editorial teams. See this - <https://job-boards.eu.greenhouse.io/plos> - page.

New LNLs Joining Soon!

New LNLs from the University of Sunderland and from Teesside University should be formally joining us soon (giving us a full house in the North East! Hence the picture above).

We are currently looking for new LNLs within University of Exeter, University of Gloucestershire, and University of Greenwich. If you have relevant contacts there please let us know so we can follow up - contact@ukrn.org

External Conferences & Events

A few days after the LNL Retreat ends, the Manchester Open Research Conference begins (9th and 10th of June). Submissions are open for presentations and posters from anyone interested in, researching, or working in Open Research (you don't need to work at Uni of Manchester to submit). Contributions can include research projects, methodological innovations, or case studies showcasing Open Research practices. See this - <https://www.openresearch.manchester.ac.uk/conference/> - page for more information.

Reading Recommendations

MetaROR - a new platform for sharing and reviewing meta-research - has got off to quite the start. They published a piece by James Heathers, where he claimed that one in seven science publications are 'fake', as well as three reviews of Heathers' work, which were

often pretty critical of his claims. Have a read of all of that at this
- <https://metaror.org/kotahi/articles/18/index.html> - site.

Resources/Initiatives

The team at FORTT have been incredible busy. They are looking for people to contribute to an 'Open Social Psychology' text book. Contributorse are needed to do lots of different tasks (some small; some big). Have a read of this

- https://docs.google.com/document/d/19mikXC5mvxU7Oy7Euz_hXXnqHqbDfk40-WGpeiQdSno/edit?tab=t.0#heading=h.9uywlkccaw1 - Google Doc to find out more.

And they also plan to launch a diamond OA journal for replications later this year. Have a look at this - <http://replicationresearch.org> - page for more information.

Closing Remarks

If you would like to contribute, or have something that you think should be shared (especially for the Spotlight section!) please get in touch. We would love to hear from you; it's your newsletter! contact@ukrn.org